

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Ramadani, F., Rauf, R., Prayuda, R., Prihatin, P. S., & Yuza, A. F. (2022). The Strengthening of Capacity Election Supervisory Body in Regional Head Election of Kuantan Singingi Regency. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 5(4), 96-102.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.05.04.382

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but are not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

The Strengthening of Capacity Election Supervisory Body in Regional Head Election of Kuantan Singingi Regency

Fitri Ramadani¹, Rahyunir Rauf², Rendi Prayuda³, Panca Setyo Prihatin⁴, Ahmad Fitra Yuza⁵

¹ Master Candidate, Department of Government Studies, Post Graduate Program, Universitas Islam Riau.
Email: fitri_ramadani@student.uir.ac.id

² Associate Professor and Lecturer, Department of Government Studies, Post Graduate Program, Universitas Islam Riau. Email: rahyunir.ip@soc.uir.ac.id

³ Lecturer, Department of Government Studies, Post Graduate Program, Universitas Islam Riau.
Email: rendiprayuda@soc.uir.ac.id

⁴ Lecturer, Department of Government Studies, Post Graduate Program, Universitas Islam Riau.
Email: panca.ip@soc.uir.ac.id

⁵ Lecturer, Department of Government Studies, Post Graduate Program, Universitas Islam Riau. Email: fitra.ip@soc.uir.ac.id

Abstract

Election law violations always occur in every election in Indonesia. One of them is Riau Province, specifically the Kuantan Singingi Regency which is directly adjacent to the Province of West Sumatra and Jambi Province, Kuantan Singingi Regency has a fluctuating number of violations and the same violations in every general election. Thus, the need to strengthen the capacity of Election Supervisory Body in the 2020 Regional Head Election of Kuantan Singingi Regency by carrying out and extra for the election. This study aims to describe the capacity building of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency to strengthen election capacity, to describe the factors that affect the capacity building of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency to strengthen election capacity. Thus the research method uses qualitative methods. The object of the research is the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency. Result shows that the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency to strengthen the election process by conducting and through training, technical guidance, coordinator meetings, recruitment and selection and socialization of participatory strengthening. The influencing factors include leadership, commitment, networking and media information and communication. The suggestions given are the socialization of participatory supervision of supervision carried out in public open spaces and improvement of regulations related to the authority of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency to impose sanctions for violators of the Regional Head Election Law.

Keywords: Capacity, Election, Supervisory Body

1. Introduction

General Election is a means of implementing People's Sovereignty which is carried out directly, publicly, freely, confidentially, honestly and fairly. Elections are held with the aim of electing people's representatives at both the

central and regional government levels, as well as to form a democratic, strong government, and gain popular support in the context of realizing national goals as mandated by the preamble to the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. Elections implemented by the Indonesian state in the context of realizing people's sovereignty as well as implementing democratic principles or values, increasing people's political awareness to actively participate in general elections for the realization of the ideals of a democratic Indonesian society.

Through the election, it is hoped that the ongoing political process will give birth to a government that is legitimate, democratic and truly represents the interests of the voting community. In order to achieve an independent and free from the influence of various parties, an institution that plays a role in supervising the implementation of the election in accordance with the laws and regulations is needed. The General Elections Supervisory Body of the Republic of Indonesia (Election Supervisory Body) is one of the election organizers that is independent and free from various parties as well as related to the implementation of its duties and authorities. The implementation of Election Supervisory Body's duties and authorities is regulated in Law number 7 of 2017 concerning General Elections.

In order to carry out the mandate of Presidential Regulation number 29 of 2014 concerning Performance Accountability System for Government Agencies, Election Supervisory Body has the obligation to independently plan, implement, measure and monitor performance and report it to higher institutions. This is stated in the Government Agency Performance Report. Election Supervisory Body provides an explanation of the achievement of the RI Bawaslu performance during the 2018 fiscal year. The 2018 performance results are measured through the 2018 Performance Agreement as a benchmark and description of the success rate of Election Supervisory Body's performance achievement for 1 year.

Direct elections are one form of efforts to improve the quality of a democratic country. Direct elections are the basis for granting the right to the people to participate directly in political life. The purpose of direct elections is that governance can be based on the will and needs of the people. Thus, holding direct elections is not only a requirement for fulfilling democracy. Formally but also must be in accordance with the essence of democracy itself, namely based on the principle of fairness and justice based on the will of the people's heart.

However, the reality of direct elections does not necessarily run according to the rules of election law. Many deviations from direct elections have led to conflicts and electoral disputes both horizontally and vertically. Deviations in the implementation of elections always occur with the same types of violations in every election administration. It can be seen and observed in the surrounding environment that there are many cases such as money politics, black campaigns and negative campaigns, the neutrality of the state civil apparatus, violations during the campaign and the existence of voters who are not registered in the DPT. The violations that occurred in the implementation of the election were never ending. The same violations always occur in every election.

The similarity of violations in every election administration shows the ineffectiveness of supervision carried out by the Election Supervisory Body. Central Java Province has a fluctuating number of violations in every election administration. This can be seen from the data processed by the Election Supervisory Body of Central Java Province regarding reports of alleged violations in the 2013 gubernatorial election as many as 181 reports, the 2014 presidential and vice presiden elections as many as 148 reports, and the 2015 simultaneous regional head elections as many as 488 reports. This data is the reason that the capacity development of the Central Java Provincial Election Supervisory Body in carrying out the election supervisory function needs to be carried out. The purpose of election supervision carried out by the Election Supervisory Body is an effort to realize democratic elections. The mandate of the people who want the election to run cleanly without money politics, peacefully without conflict and fair without fraud is the responsibility of the role of the Election Supervisory Body. Election violations are an important task for the Election Supervisory Body because these violations can injure the essence of election administration. Thus, it is important to develop the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body because as an election supervisory agency, the Central Java Provincial Election Supervisory Body has a central role in the implementation of elections. Efforts to develop the capacity of the Central Java Provincial Election Supervisory Body in carrying out the election oversight function are carried out through systems, organization and human resource development programs.

2. Research Method

The research method uses qualitative research methods with a research background in the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency. The focus of the research includes (1) strengthening the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency in carrying out the function of election supervision, (2) factors that affect the strengthening of the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency in carrying out the function of election supervision. As well as the data collection is done by using the method of interviews, documentation and observation, while the validity of the data test using triangulation of sources and techniques. Data analysis includes data reduction, data presentation, conclusion drawing and verification. Informants in this study included the Coordinator of the Prevention and Inter-Agency Relations Division, the Coordinator of the Organization and Human Resources Division, the Coordinator of the Violation Enforcement Division, and the Assistant Division of Organization and Human Resources.

3. Results and Discussion

Strengthening the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency is seen from the capacity and ability of a person, namely the existence of a policy which means that someone who has policy or power can do everything that is realized by action, and can increase work capacity. Therefore, capacity building is an effort to improve one's skills so that Election Supervisory Body employees have more productive skills in order to achieve predetermined goals, Nasution (2011; 1). Thus, research on strengthening the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency aims to describe capacity building or commonly referred to as capacity strengthening described by experts. According to several experts, capacity building is a capacity building, capacity strengthening, and capacity building. However, there are differences in the meaning of the word building, and broadly what is being discussed is the discussion of the capacity itself. Specifically, capacity is defined as a person's ability to carry out something in order to achieve the expected orientation. This is as described by Grindle in Haryono (2012:39) "capacity building is intended to encompass a variety of strategies that have to do with increasing the efficiency, effectiveness and responsiveness of government performance". strategies that can improve the efficiency, effectiveness and responsiveness of government performance). In the process and stages of capacity building or capacity building, there are components that can be considered, namely:

- a. performance capacity, whether tools, money, equipment, consumables etc. are available to do the job.
- b. Personal capacity, i.e. the individual is knowledgeable, skilled and confident enough to do something right.
- c. Workload capacity, whether there are staff with broad enough skills to cope with the workload.
- d. Supervisory capacity, reporting and monitoring systems in place, clear accountability for physical supervisors to monitor staff under them and effective incentives and sanctions in place.
- e. Facility capacity, whether the training center site is large enough with the right staff in sufficient numbers.
- f. Support service capacity, whether there are laboratories, training institutes, administrative staff and facilities.

From the opinions of the experts above, it can be understood that capacity building is a process or activity to improve the ability of a person, group, organization or system in order to create better performance and be responsive to environmental changes so as to achieve goals. There are three things that can be understood from capacity building or capacity strengthening, namely: increasing human resources, strengthening organizations and systems, namely institutional reform. In this case, according to Grindle dal Haryono (2009:39) suggests that a strengthening or development of human resource capacity is "initiatives to develop human resources generally seek the capacity of individuals to carry out their professional and technical responsibilities". The movement to develop human resources in general seeks to increase the capacity of individuals in carrying out their responsibilities professionally and improve their technical abilities. Haryono (2012).

In various terms of capacity and capacity building of human resources, it can be seen that capacity building is seen through a cycle of capacity development stages consisting of five stages, namely stakeholder involvement, capacity assessment, determining capacity development responses, implementing capacity development responses, and evaluating capacity development. In this case, strengthening the capacity of human resources is

also needed by the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency, namely with strength and policies, which means that someone who has the policy or power can do everything that is realized by action, can increase work capacity. Therefore, capacity building is an effort to improve one's skills so that employees have more productive skills in order to achieve predetermined goals, Nasution (2011: 1).

Strengthening the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency in carrying out the function of election supervision, based on the results of research carried out through efforts to develop human resources and organizational development. This development is an effort by the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency to achieve the goal of its supervisory function, namely the creation of democratic elections. Meanwhile, UNDP in Haryanto (2014: 20) explains that capacity monitoring is a process to improve the ability of a person, organization or system to achieve a predetermined goal. In this case, efforts to achieve the goal of creating democratic elections through strengthening the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency in carrying out the function of strengthening and supervising elections are carried out as an initiative to improve supervisory performance.

Meanwhile, the notion of performance According to Nawawi (2013) performance is a result achieved by the employee in a particular job, employee performance can be seen from the following indicators:

- a. Decisions on all the rules that have been set by the organization
- b. Can carry out tasks or work without errors or with the lowest error rate
- c. Determination in carrying out tasks

In this case, according to Gibson (1996) employee performance is the desired outcome of the perpetrator. Employee performance is the level against which employees achieve job requirements (Simamora: 2004). Performance appraisal generally includes both qualitative and quantitative aspects of the performance of the work. According to Mathis (206: 113) the factors that influence employee performance are the employee's ability to work, the level of effort devoted, and the organizational support he receives. Employee performance is how he does everything related to a job related to the organization. Performance (performance) is a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of a program of activities or policies in realizing the target. The goals of the organization's vision and mission are outlined through the strategic planning of an organization. Sutrisno (2015). According to Marsono (1996:2) the general election is a tool whose use should not cause damage to the foundations of democracy and even cause things to tell the people, but must ensure the success of the New Order struggle. 32, namely the upholding of Pancasila and the preservation of the 1945 Constitution. Election supervision is a process in determining performance measures and taking action to support the achievement of the expected results in accordance with the performance targets that have been set. In the next section, supervision is a process to ensure that all activities carried out are in accordance with what has been planned. Yosa (2010).

In the context of public management, supervision is an important aspect to keep government functions running properly, so that supervision is important with the implementation of good governance. Sadjijono (2008). Meanwhile, according to the administrative law approach, supervision or strengthening is defined as a process of comparing activities against what is carried out, implemented, or carried out with what is desired, planned or ordered. The results of supervision must be able to show the extent to which there is a match and a mismatch, to further find the causes of the problems that arise.

In Law No. 15 of 2011 concerning General Election Organizers Article 1 paragraph 16 it is stated that Election Supervisory Body is an election management agency tasked with overseeing election organizers throughout the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia (NKRI). Election Supervisory Body has organizational equipment, including Provincial Election Supervisory Body, Regency/City Election Supervisory Committee, Sub-district, Field Election Supervisor located in village or other designations as well as Overseas Election Supervisor on duty in other countries.

Based on Law No. 15 of 2011 it is stated that Election Supervisory Body and its staff are tasked with overseeing the implementation of the General Election in the context of preventing and taking action against violations for the realization of a democratic election. In accordance with the slogan that is often conveyed in various Election

Supervisory Body forums, namely "result-oriented prevention and process-oriented action". Furthermore, in election supervision according to Article 1 Number 25 of Election Supervisory Body Regulation Number 11 of 2014 concerning General Election Supervision, it is the activity of observing, reviewing, examining and assessing the process of organizing elections in accordance with the laws and regulations.

In a process to define what is to be achieved, and its approach to managing and strengthening people in a way that can increase the likelihood that the goals will be achieved within a certain period of time either short or in the future. Performance management processes can be used to communicate and reinforce organizational strategies, values and norms and integrate individual and organizational goals. One of the implementations of technical guidance carried out is related to the 12 election monitoring modules. Through technical guidance carried out by the Kuantan Singingi Regency Election Supervisory Body to the Sub-district supervisory body, the strengthening of election supervision can be communicated regarding how and strategies to be carried out so that the monitoring targets and targets can be achieved in accordance with the 12 election monitoring modules.

This is as Dharma (2013: 25) argues that performance management is a process to determine what must be achieved, and its approach to managing and developing human beings in a way that can increase the likelihood that goals will be achieved within a certain period of time, both short and long. Third, the coordination meeting is a capacity building on the organizational dimension in the form of developing organizational culture. One example of coordination meeting activities is the coordination meeting for monitoring the updating of data and voter lists. Based on the research results, the coordination meeting is intended to ensure that every citizen who meets the requirements as a voter is registered in the voter list. Through the coordination meeting, the organizational culture that will be realized is the alignment of perceptions of supervision from the submission of DP4 (Data on Population Potential Election Voters) which has been consolidated, verified and validated by the government to the KPU, to the supervision of the determination and announcement of the DPS (Temporary Voters List), DPT (Permanent Voter List) and additional voter registration. The coordination meeting for monitoring the updating of data and voter lists was conducted to equalize perceptions of the methods and steps for monitoring the updating of data and voter lists as well as to align perceptions of the follow-up to reports of alleged violations found. With this common perception, there will be limits to the control of actions that can be taken which is a shared commitment among election supervisors.

Siagian (2004: 65) states that a strong organizational culture has the function of determining the limits of acceptable behavior, fostering a sense of belonging, increasing the ability to make commitments for the success of the organization, maintaining social stability within the organization, and controlling and supervising the behavior of members of the organization concerned. It can be said that the coordination meeting is one of the efforts to form an organizational culture in the supervisory function. Fourth, the recruitment and selection of the Sub-district Election Supervisory Body is a capacity building on the human resource dimension. Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency by conducting open recruitment of Sub-district Election Supervisory Body. Recruitment is carried out to attract prospective employees who have the abilities and criteria that are in accordance with the needs of the organization. Thus, the open recruitment conducted by the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency is intended to attract many applicants for prospective members of the Supervisory Committee who have high integrity in accordance with the needs of supervision. This is as stated by Simamora (2001: 212) that a series of activities in the recruitment process include finding and attracting job applicants with the motivation, abilities, skills and knowledge needed to cover the deficiencies identified in staffing planning. Recruitment activities begin when candidates are searched for and end when their applications are submitted. Through recruitment, individuals who have the required skills are encouraged to apply for available job vacancies. The results of the recruitment are a group of job applicants who will be selected to become new employees. The recruitment process carried out by the Kuantan Singingi Regency Election Supervisory Body selection team began with the socialization of registration, the implementation of the Sub-district Election Supervisory Body registration to the submission of files by applicants.

This is because in the selection applicants are asked to write a paper which must then be presented and be able to account for what they have written. The selection of candidates for the Sub-district Election Supervisory Body must produce members of the Sub-district Election Supervisory Body who have high integrity in supervising the

election, so the selection process must be carried out selectively and competitively. The selection process is as conveyed by Triyono (2012: 44) that in a series of employee selection processes, companies or organizations must be able to choose the best prospective employees and in accordance with the required fields and eliminate applicants who are considered inappropriate to be accepted in a job in the organization or organization. company. The selection process is basically a systematic effort carried out to better ensure that those who are accepted are considered the most appropriate, either with predetermined criteria or the required number. Strengthening the capacity of the Kuantan Singingi Regency Election Supervisory Body in carrying out its supervisory function is certainly inseparable from the factors that influence it. Several factors that influence the strengthening of the capacity of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency in carrying out the election oversight function include leadership, joint commitment, networks and information. Adaptive leadership is carried out by providing wide opportunities for every component of the organization, including personal resources to initiate the development of institutional capacity towards.

Achievement of desired organizational goals. The leadership of the Kuantan Singingi Regency Election Supervisory Body in addition to providing direction and guidance also has the authority of a leader who can be used as an example. The ideal leader will be able to place as an example, advisor, mentor and motivator for those he leads. Second, the joint commitment made by each member of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency is to reduce the number of election violations through a violation prevention strategy. This commitment was carried out well by all leaders and employees of the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency. The shared commitment of each member of the Election Supervisory Body Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency is as stated by Haryanto (2014: 30) that joint commitment can be carried out through the involvement of all organizational actors in supporting the success of the institution's capacity building program. Shared commitment is the basic capital that must be continuously developed and maintained properly because it will be the basis of the entire design of activities that will be carried out by an organization. Third, the network of cooperation. The network of cooperation is carried out by the Kuantan Singingi Regency Election Supervisory Body with several universities, mass organizations and local governments. This is done with the aim of conducting supervision in terms of prevention or handling of violations. Through this collaboration, the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency has developed a broad supervisory function, not only for the institution itself. This is as stated by Haryanto (2014: 31) that the institutional capacity development process cannot be carried out by institutional ego, but needs to be carried out in collaboration with stakeholders. Fourth, information and communication media. Submission and receipt of information at the Election Supervisory Body of Kuantan Singingi Regency is carried out transparently and easily accessible to the general public. Through the ease of access to this information, it is possible for the public to provide feedback based on the environmental conditions of the community related to the information they receive.

4. Conclusion

Strengthening the capacity of the General Elections Supervisory Agency (Election Supervisory Body) of Kuantan Singingi Regency in carrying out the function of monitoring and strengthening elections is carried out on strengthening organizational capacity and human resources. First, strengthening organizational capacity consists of strengthening capacity in organizational performance management through technical guidance activities and capacity building on organizational culture through coordination meeting activities. Second, strengthening human resource capacity consists of capacity building in human resource education and training through training of trainers for members and assistant supervisory divisions as well as socialization activities for participatory supervision and strengthening to the community, and capacity strengthening in the recruitment and selection of members of the Sub-district Election Supervisory Body. The capacity building carried out by the Kuantan Singingi Regency Election Supervisory Body is an effort to optimize the supervisory function both carried out by the Kuantan Singingi Regency Election Supervisory Body and the election supervisory institutions under it. Factors that influence the strengthening of the capacity of the General Elections Supervisory Body (Election Supervisory Body) of Kuantan Singingi Regency include: (1) representative leadership with three leaders in each field and democratic leadership, (2) shared commitment of each Election Supervisory Body member Kuantan Singingi Regency in making efforts to reduce the number of election violations through prevention strategies, (3) establishing a network of cooperation with local governments, mass organizations and universities in carrying out

supervisory functions, especially in preventing election violations, and (4) Through the media of information and transparent and easily accessible communication through social media such as websites and Facebook as well as monthly newsletters. Suggestions in this study are that participatory supervision socialization activities should not only be carried out through socialization activities in closed spaces, but can also be carried out in open spaces, and an improvement in the regulation of Law No. 15 of 2011 concerning Election Organizers related to the articles of authority of Regency Election Supervisory Body in impose sanctions.

References

- Ayon. (2012). *New Paradigm of Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Love Books. Law Number 15 of 2011 concerning Election Organizers.
- Curran, K. (2018). E-Voting on the Blockchain. *The Journal of The British Blockchain Association*, 1(2), 1–6. [https://doi.org/10.31585/jbba-1-2-\(3\)2018](https://doi.org/10.31585/jbba-1-2-(3)2018)
- Dharma, Surya. (2013). *Performance Management Philosophy, Theory and Its Application*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.
- Durán, I. M. (2018). Television and electoral results in Catalonia. *SERIEs*, 9(4), 423–456. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13209-018-0183-3>
- Haryanto. (2014). *Institutional Capacity Development*. Jakarta: AP2I Pres.
- Holliday, W. H., & Pacuit, E. (2019). Strategic Voting Under Uncertainty About the Voting Method. *Electronic Proceedings in Theoretical Computer Science*, 297, 252–272. <https://doi.org/10.4204/EPTCS.297.17>
- Hong, V. T. A. (2016, July 6). Infographic: Vietnam's 2016 national elections. *Customnews.Vn*. <https://customsnews.vn/infographic-vietnams-2016-national-elections-43.html>
- Kongkirati, P. (2016). Thailand's Failed 2014 Election: The Anti-Election Movement, Violence and Democratic Breakdown. *Journal of Contemporary Asia*, 46(3), 467–485. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00472336.2016.1166259>
- Kristensen, N. N., & Solhaug, T. (2016). Students as First-time Voters: The Role of Voter Advice Applications in Self-reflection on Party Choice and Political Identity. *Journal of Social Science Education*, 15(3), 32–42. <https://doi.org/10.4119/UNIBI/jsse-v16-i1-1503>
- Lamprianou, I. (2013). *Contemporary Political Participation Research: A Critical Assessment*. Springer Verlag Berlin Heidelberg. DOI 10.1007/978-3-642-30068-4_2
- Lane, M. (2019). The 2019 Indonesian Elections: An Overview. *Perspective*, 49(14June), 1–9.
- Saputra, Trio, and Rendi Prayuda. "PARTICIPATORY VILLAGE DEVELOPMENT PLANNING MODEL." *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology* 17.5 (2020): 324-336.
- Siagian, Son. (2004). *21st Century Management*. Jakarta: Earth Literacy.
- Simamora, Henry. (2001). *Human Resource Management*. Yogyakarta: STIE YKPN. Triyono,
- Stadelmann, D., & Torgler, B. (2013). Bounded Rationality and Voting Decisions over 160 Years: Voter Behavior and Increasing Complexity in Decision-Making. *PLoS ONE*, 8(12), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0084078>
- Stott, D. A. (2019). Indonesia's 2019 Elections: Democracy Consolidated? *The Asia-Pacific Journal*, 17(6), 1– 19.
- Strengthening Electoral Processes and Democratic Practices in Cambodia: Report on Forums on Elections and Democratic Space (pp. 1–49). (2011). [Forums on Elections And Democratic Space Project]. Cambodian Center for Human Right. <https://cchrcambodia.org/admin/media/report/report/english/2011-07-20-report-eng.pdf>
- Stuart-Fox, M. (2007). LAOS: Politics in a Single-party State. *Southeast Asian Affairs*, 161–180. JSTOR.